

MESS 0019

Electrometeorology 2.1 - The 2021 Mayfield, Kentucky Tornado Track and the New Madrid gravity & magnetic anomalies

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the author continues a similar analysis as MESS0018¹, with overlapping gravity and magnetic anomaly data. Only this paper hones in on the New Madrid Fault Zone and the long track tornado of Dec. 10, 2021, for a direct overlay. No statistical heuristics is needed to see this is past correlation and into causation territory. Further meta-analysis and direct statistical analysis is needed to see just how the causation mechanism works: where is the anode, the cathode, how did the escarpments form (compare with lab work) vs. how do storms spool up to generate the long track vortical electric circuits? Some solar wind data from Dec. 8-10 reveals only one remarkable aspect: a 14x increase in proton density on the 10th may have caused the storm to seed in the remarkably late period of the year. Temperatures that day were in the 70s F (Memphis was 79 F)². The unusualness of the EF4 makes it all that more of a beacon for analysis, especially considering other tectonic and electrogeology features in the region.

Keywords: Mayfield- Tornado - Earthquake - Magnetism - Gravity - Solar Proton Density - New Madrid Fault

1

https://www.academia.edu/88366256/MESS0018_GEO_2_2_Electrogeology_evidence_in_macrolytic_magnetic_and_gravitic_field_anomalies_in_VA_NC_and_KY_associated_with_surface_gravity_anomalies

² <https://www.washingtonpost.com/weather/2021/12/11/tornado-path-mayfield-kentucky-deaths/>

The Unusual December 2021 Mayfield, Kentucky EF4 Tornado

Figure 1 - December 10, 2021 Mayfield “Quad-State” Tornado origin track; credit: Dexter

Figure 2 - Predicted 2021 tracks; commonly long track tornadoes have historically moved along these tracks.

Note to the reader: one thing that Arkansas has in common with Kentucky is the large quartz crystal matrices beneath the states. There is a large amount of these crystals in and around Little Rock, AR.

There is almost certainly no coincidence with the special folding of the mountains there, which enable the hot springs to function - and stay hot -

and the crystals, and the anomalies there.

Figure 3 - Gravity Anomalies of Texarkana region; The tornado origins come from the anomaly proximal to the AB region. The specific tornado in question began near to the large matrix anomaly. The attraction of the western KY (Mississippian region) perhaps attracted the tornadoes from the Arkansas region.

Special note, look at the AGG region in Figure 4 laying (as reported in MESS0018) directly to the east of the Blue Ridge Mountains.

Credit: Gravity map in Texarkana region, ScienceDirect.com³

Credit: NGS/NOAA⁴

Figure 5 - Arkansas magnetic anomaly, escarpments etched out; credit: USGS⁵

From top to bottom the arrows represent:

- The common origin location for storms (see Figure 2)
- The magnetic flux and spaced sinusoidal concentrations that are uncoincidentally in the same line of direction as the long-track tornado pathways
- The region where a large cathode, magnetic escarpment occurred. The geology above this region is folded mountain chains, where hot springs are common.

³ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/bouguer-anomaly>

⁴ https://www.ngs.noaa.gov/PUBS_LIB/GEOID/Droman_papers/Published/Peerevw_NGS/tle2104r0366.pdf

⁵ <https://pubs.usgs.gov/ds/352/arkla.html>

A bit strange that there are more concentrations inside. Perhaps there are similar features to kimberlites under these magnetic structures?

Figure 7- Overlay of Figure 11 from MESS0018⁶ with Figure 6 (tornado track, 2021); credit: The Independent⁷

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⁷ <https://www.independent.co.uk/climate-change/news/kentucky-tornado-map-path-latest-b1975194.html>

In Figure 7 we see cloisters of Earthquakes (inexplicably?⁸) and interactions with the meteorological evidence. Also, we see clusters of them at the upper edge of Hick's Dome, where electrogeology is A++ evidence, and is in an arcing relationship to the Land Between the Lakes. And note there are no earthquakes in this arch. We also see a fairly large earthquake near Mayfield. This is not expected, and one should consult the gravity anomaly map (figure 10). Note also the odd organ circled dearth of earthquakes, with suddenly two in the middle. (the red/orange is part of the New Madrid Zone). Finally note how the weather chain crosses the pink arrow's flux, and arches (curvature of the Earth?) into the purple arrow's flux. Very many earthquakes are clearly related to this arcing flux.

Figure 8- Geological and Geophysical Maps of the Illinois Basin-Ozark Dome Region Map; credit: Albert et al⁹

Note the Magnetic anomaly right at Mayfield. Does the overlap of electrogravitics and magnetics indicate a beacon for a long-track tornado? Tornadoes will be discussed after the MET 2.2 paper.

⁸ Fracking data?

⁹ https://www.isgs.illinois.edu/sites/isgs/files/maps/statewide/imap23_10_magnetic_anomaly_web.pdf

The use of the magnetic map, in this detail, in combining and comparing with the previous map, will now be done. However, the data from Figure 5 also has to be stitched in.

A red pentagon was added around one cloister of earthquakes located at the left end of the tornado pathways (which are common, by the by).

Figure 9 - Figure 7 & 8 overlapped, with transparency at 50%

Figure 10 - Overlapping Gravity map with Figure 8 & 10; credit: Albert et al¹⁰/author

Figure 11 - Transition of transparency (gif); credit: author¹¹

Finally, busy as it is, the overlap of weather (arrows) with magnetics and gravity indicate an impossible (statistically speaking) 'coincidence' and this is beyond correlation. We are definitely within causation territory. The only question is, without determining the anode and cathode location determinants, we cannot assign the causation. To do this, in a future paper, an overlap with

10

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Geological-and-geophysical-maps-of-the-Illinois-Abert-Marshak/bc46bea12127bc3bfc47646abf0e216012dd5cc0/figure/8>

¹¹ <https://makeagif.com/i/yFCnJx>

waterflow/table, fracking, and mineral map data is absolutely necessary to determine the multi-layer causation data which can then inform us about the high/low pressure zones, the Earth Spots, and other various intrigues which will finally determine causality. In the meantime the author also suggests an engineering of a statistical analysis of this type of research. As far as the author knows, this is all new ground - electro-geo-meterology (EGM). It certainly is in electrogeology.

Solar Wind Data

The tornado occurred on December 10, 2021. The following is the four day leadup data for the spaceweather (courtesy spaceweather.com):

Table 1 - Space Weather Data

<i>Dec. 7</i>	<i>Dec. 8</i>	<i>Dec. 9</i>	<i>Dec. 10</i>
<p>Solar wind speed: 413.1 km/sec density: 8.0 protons/cm³ more data: ACE, DSCOVR Updated: Today at 2345 UT</p>	<p>Solar wind speed: 385.6 km/sec density: 3.7 protons/cm³ more data: ACE, DSCOVR Updated: Today at 2240 UT</p>	<p>Solar wind speed: 329.2 km/sec density: 2.3 protons/cm³ more data: ACE, DSCOVR Updated: Today at 2346 UT</p>	<p>Solar wind speed: 328.8 km/sec density: 28.1 protons/cm³ more data: ACE, DSCOVR Updated: Today at 2344 UT</p>
<p>X-ray Solar Flares 6-hr max: B1 1905 UT Dec07 24-hr: B1 1905 UT Dec07 explanation more data Updated: Today at: 2350 UT</p>	<p>X-ray Solar Flares 6-hr max: A1 1807 UT Dec08 24-hr: A4 1714 UT Dec08 explanation more data Updated: Today at: 2350 UT</p>	<p>X-ray Solar Flares 6-hr max: A7 2347 UT Dec09 24-hr: A6 2345 UT Dec09 explanation more data Updated: Today at: 2350 UT</p>	<p>X-ray Solar Flares 6-hr max: A5 2342 UT Dec10 24-hr: A7 0013 UT Dec10 explanation more data Updated: Today at: 2350 UT</p>
<p>Daily Sun: 07 Dec 21</p>			

Figures 12-15 the sun; credit: spaceweather.com

Other than a B class flare on the 7th, the only remarkable item is the 14x increase in proton density on the 10th. That is a startling, even alarming, correlation with the CDN/Electric Field in clinic (in situ) medical research by the author, and bears further statistical analysis. Sunspots, velocity, and other data is clearly unremarkable.

Analysis & Conclusion

The final overlay in Figure 10 (and 11) is truly revelatory. Even beyond the already surprising results of MESS0018! What we see here is better than the author even suspected on the Pulse call in December-January 2021-2022. It's uncanny where the system started dropping tornados in the magnetic flux and earthquake cloister. The fact that then the EF4 tornado burst through Mayfield - regrettably - at full strength right over the earthquake zone where a gravity anomaly exists... statistically it is unheard of.

The missing elements, as mentioned before and in MESS0018, are the following needed layers (in a format that is less clunky than used here):

- Freshwater/groundwater pools and flow analysis (subsurface bathymetry)
- Crystalline and mineral resource depositions in the New Madrid Zone
- Fracking and earthquake data (differentiated with the typical, larger 'tectonic' earthquakes)
- Heat or radiative flux
- Magnetic field lines (Earth/atmosphere)
- Airflow, particularly average models for the year OR at least in the spring, and in this case winter¹².

Additionally, an extra layer of solar wind data processing is probably warranted when looking for Davidson¹³-Uyen¹⁴ "Earth spots"¹⁵, and while it is clear that the sun isn't particularly a major contributor in terms of lead up, it is entirely likely that the wide variation in flux concentration is an absolute potential trigger for these types of events. In MET 2.2, more work into the previously proposed Hall-Thornhill/Leybourne-Scott Tornado circuit (Planetary Electric Circuit level) will be provided, along with some surprising data out of the mainstream. The combination of these and the latest GEO works, will lead to an excellent discussion in the Spheres of Heaven model¹⁶. Finally these works take us much closer to the understanding of HEGEME theory¹⁷, and perhaps the next stages of EGM and other geophysical models.

References

1. "MESS0019: MET 2.1 - KY Tornadoe New Madrid Zone & magnetics," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uD7wGiQXggXemKmAg1wAvcl9BY9lsG6yz763-4OEL0g/edit>
2. "MESS0018: GEO 2.2 -Electrogeology evidence in macrolytic magnetic and gravitic field anomalies in VA, NC, and KY associated with surface gravity anomalies," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/88366256/MESS0018_GEO_2_2_Electrogeology_evidence_in_macrolytic_magnetic_and_gravitic_field_anomalies_in_VA_NC_and_KY_associated_with_surface_gravity_anomalies
3. "How Friday night's rare and deadly December tornado outbreak unfolded," The Washington Post, J. Samenoe, J. Feuerstein & I. Living, 2021, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/weather/2021/12/11/tornado-path-mayfield-kentucky-deaths/>
4. "Bouguer Anomaly," ScienceDirect/Encyclopedia of Geology, K.C. Nielsen, 2005, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/bouguer-anomaly>

¹² Winter is known for much more electrostatic involvement.

¹³ <https://www.amazon.com/Weathermans-Guide-Sun-Ben-Davidson/dp/148358898X/>

¹⁴ <https://suspiciousobservers.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Paper-1.pdf>

¹⁵ <https://suspiciousobservers.org/electric-earth-sun/>

¹⁶ MESS0023 ^

¹⁷

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

5. "Upgraded gravity anomaly base of the United States," ngs.noaa.gov, G. R. Keller et al, 2002.
https://www.ngs.noaa.gov/PUBS_LIB/GEOID/Droman_papers/Published/Peerevw_NGS/tle2104r0366.pdf
6. "Arkansas and Louisiana Merged Aeromagnetic Anomaly Map," U.S. Department of the Interior | U.S. Geological Survey, 2016, <https://pubs.usgs.gov/ds/352/arkla.html>
7. "Kentucky tornado: Map shows path of possible 'longest single-track twister' wreaking havoc," Independent, G. Kilander, 2021,
<https://www.independent.co.uk/climate-change/news/kentucky-tornado-map-path-latest-b1975194.html>
8. "Geological and Geophysical Maps of the Illinois Basin-Ozark Dome Region: Map 10 Magnetic Anomaly," Illinois.edu, C. C. Abert, S. Marshak & T. H. Larson, 2016,
https://files.isgs.illinois.edu/sites/default/files/maps/statewide/imap23_10_magnetic_anomaly_web.pdf
9. "Real Time Solar Wind," NOAA.gov, <https://www.swpc.noaa.gov/products/real-time-solar-wind>
10. "The Classification of X-ray Solar Flares or "Solar Flare Alphabet Soup" Space Weather.com,
<https://spaceweather.com/glossary/flareclasses.html>
11. "Goes X-Ray Flux (Dynamic Plot), Space Weather Prediction Center,
<https://www.swpc.noaa.gov/products/goes-x-ray-flux-dynamic-plot>
12. "Weatherman's Guide to the Sun: First Edition," Amazon, D. Davidson, 2017,
<https://www.amazon.com/Weathermans-Guide-Sun-Ben-Davidson/dp/148358898X/>
13. "Relationship Between M8 + Earthquake Occurrences and The Solar Polar Magnetic Fields" New Concepts in Global Tectonics Journal, V. 3, No. 3, B. Davidson, K. U-YEN & C. Holloman, 2015,
<https://suspicious0bservers.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Paper-1.pdf>
14. "Electric Earth and Sun," Space Weather News, 2022, <https://suspicious0bservers.org/electric-earth-sun/>
15. "MESS0023: the Spheres of Heaven in the HEGEME," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022
[MESS0023: MET 2.22 - The Spheres of Heaven in the HEGEME](#)
16. "Our Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky Application of Hollow-Expanding-Growing-Electromagnetic Earth Hypothesis with particular respect to the Earth's Atmosphere starting from the Lithosphere and ascending Altitude," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018,
https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude